

PECULIARITIES OF PROJECT MANAGEMENT IN THE FIELD OF HOUSING AND UTILITIES IN SPOD-, VUCA AND BANI-WORLD CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

The presented article investigates the issues of formation of managerial trends using synectic-sense modeling in the management of projects in the sphere of housing and communal services. Such a need, according to the authors, has arisen due to the special characteristics of the modern world – “fragility”, high anxiety, non-linearity of development, the need to choose priorities, “indeterminate, uncertainty”. A comparative analysis of the paradigms of rationality in the framework of the transition to the post-non-classical picture of the world is carried out. The tools of influence on the enterprise management system are identified: organizational culture and organizational structure. The model of binary characteristics of the management system in the languages of SPOD-, VUCA and BANI-world is shown. The importance of measures to improve organizational culture, overcoming resistance to change, which is an important prerequisite for the formation of a flexible modern enterprise of housing and communal services in a highly uncertain environment, is noted. The article presents the methodology of using such a tool as synectic and semantic modeling, which allows to form management trends. The final part of the article concludes that it is advisable to use synectic-sense modeling in the formation of management trends and modeling of the future.

Keywords: trend, synectic and semantic modeling, project management, future, management trends, management systems.

Relation to scientific and practical tasks.

The relevance of specifying the target function of the economy of Ukraine as a system in the changing VUCA – world is determined by the multi-criteriality of assessing the effectiveness of economic processes and the diversity of interests of their participants, which come into conflict at the stages of crisis development of society. Identification of fundamental goals of functioning of economic systems allows to form an objective basis for their management, the dominance of which over subjective factors determines the long-term and sustainable ability to fulfill the functions inherent in them from nature.

Analyzing recent studies and publications.

In the conditions of economic transformation, its transition to digital reality, an integral part of any system management is compliance with the requirements and challenges that are constantly emerging in the process of digitalization of all spheres of social life. The 21st century is becoming the century of information, when in every sphere of the national economy huge data arrays are operated, which have a permanent impact on the economy and all economic entities. Within the framework of world models, this process is described as a transition from SPOD- to VUCA and BANI-world. Of course, such transformation affects all components and subsystems. There arises the problem of the need to make changes in the current management model, which has recently been effective. The management model of a modern housing and utilities enterprise as a system becomes in these conditions a flexible and active process, the transformation of the management language takes place, its system changes. Activation of

all components of the management system is a complex process and affects both the structure of the organization and its organizational culture. According to Kuznetsov S. A., the construction of a model of active culture begins with its deep foundations: “the definition of meanings and values, and then, consistently moving to more superficial layers, norms of behavior and guidelines of activity, is completed at the level of manifestations of culture in objects, systems, relationships and processes of life activity of the organization” [1, p. 128]. This is the self-deployment of organizational culture with the help of several components: meanings, values, norms of behavior, guidelines of activity, as well as material manifestations of culture. No management system can act autonomously and is strongly influenced by external factors, microenvironmental factors and stakeholders' activities. In this regard, a manager at any level faces a difficult task of making effective management decisions that, on the one hand, correspond to external conditions and would be expedient, and, on the other hand, would fit into the management model that operates at the enterprise. It is this harmony that allows to ensure the successful development of the organization and its high competitiveness in the market. Unfortunately, it is very problematic to achieve such harmony in practice because there are obstacles at one or another level within the management system (in the organization), which are called resistance, because all innovations and innovations are implemented in the struggle against tradition. Resistance to change at the enterprise can be active or passive, open or hidden, but it is a natural and inherent pro-

cess, which is inherent in all management systems. According to Popova N., Shynkarenko V., Kryvoruchko O., Zéman Z., “the process of resistance to change is influenced by a whole set of reasons of economic, organizational, personal, social, informational and other plan” [2, p. 55]. According to the authors of the article, this resistance can be minimized not only by a long-term process of forming an active organizational culture of the enterprise, but also by more local means within the framework of setting goals and objectives of the innovation plan.

Purpose of the article.

The focus of the article is the transformation of the management model of the housing and utilities enterprise in the conditions of transition from SPOD- to VUCA and BANI-world to maintain a stable position in the housing and utilities market and increase competitiveness.

Presentation of the main material. Justification of the obtained results.

In the scientific literature, when analyzing the digitalization of the economy, much attention is paid to technical and technological changes, while organizational and management issues are left aside. And to create a holistic system, there must be harmony between these interrelated components. This is a mandatory requirement for the effective implementation of innovative technologies in any organization. If we consider the issue of formation of the scientific picture of the world and its evolution, we can draw many analogies to the issues of formation of the economic system, and, accordingly, the production system as a unit at the level of microeconomics. Let us specify that “the picture of the world is a set of ideas about the structure of the reality surrounding a person, as well as the ways of its functioning and development developed at a particular stage of human development” [3, p. 174].

The issue of transformation and transition to digital reality in scientific literature is described as the transition from SPOD-world to VUCA-world through the fourth industrial revolution, the mass spread of artificial intelligence and digital technologies. The models of governance in these systems must be radically different, as has been shown by comparing different scientific worldviews. Let us consider these models in more detail.

SPOD model is a stable, defined system applicable to the whole world, where the key parameters are the following features: steady – stability; predictable – predictability; ordinary – simplicity; definite – certainty. If we talk about the management paradigm in such a model, it will be based on passive characteristics, as any organizational system operates in conditions of certainty, can independently determine the guidelines and directions of development. Planning horizons at this level are calculated in years, and the system is stable and amenable to forecasting, and therefore effective strategic planning. Along with the classical one, this corresponds to the non-classical scientific picture of the world, as the latter is based on the theory of relativity and the probability of occurrence of a particular outcome can be calculated. The management system within the framework of these scientific pictures of the

world corresponds to the SPOD-world, based on certainty, albeit temporally limited. Any management system should be relevant and correspond to the conditions of external and internal environment.

Similarly, to the post-non-classical scientific picture, the new conditions within which the VUCA-world paradigm emerged have formed modern, already active characteristics: volatility – instability; uncertainty – uncertainty; complexity – complexity; ambiguity – ambiguity. Thus, the mentioned features are the opposite of the previous model. Accordingly, the vital necessity of enterprises is the reorientation of the current management system to the one dictated by market conditions. A high degree of uncertainty complicates all management processes, including planning. If in the previous model we talked about strategic planning measured in years, in these conditions one can confidently plan only for a few months. We can talk about this transformation in the conditions of transition from non-classical to post-non-classical scientific picture of the world, there are new challenges of the external environment, which is subject to constant changes.

Consequently, a management system that can successfully function in a VUCA-world must be active and flexible. Accordingly, the system of priority values changes, caused by the transition from passive to active organizational culture. This issue can be considered in the context of different groups of employees, such as managers, professionals, and workers. In these groups, depending on the unit and position held, the level of activation of organizational culture may differ, but there should be a tendency to reduce passivity in all categories.

An important element of activation of production activity is the factors of the internal environment of the organization. The value system of organizational culture acts in this case as an activity management system and should meet certain requirements, carry such characteristics as:

- innovativeness, which becomes a necessary factor in the activity of not only managers and specialists, but also workers, as the system of innovation potential of the enterprise affects all categories and groups of employees;
- flexibility (non-linearity), which is the ability to constantly adjust to the conditions dictated by the market in terms of decision-making, control and execution;
- subjectivity, which represents in this case the orientation not on its own production, but a strict dependence on external conditions, for example, the challenges of macroeconomic factors, contact environment or the requirements of consumers, who are the key player in the VUCA-world;
- decentralization, which implies a comprehensive increase in the delegation of certain powers and management functions in order to improve their efficiency in the conditions of huge amounts of information;
- initiative, which should be objective and come from different categories and groups of workers, which in the conditions of VUCA-world can be an opportunity for development;

- criticality, which is a constructive analytical process aimed at developing new management decisions or adjusting plans, tasks, results.

VUCA-world is a dynamic system, constantly changing and subject to challenges of economic, political, technical-technological, and other nature. On the one hand, it opens new opportunities for enterprises and organizations, and on the other hand, it builds barriers related to the uncertainty of the market situation. To build an effective management system in the housing and utilities sector, it is necessary to transform and re-direct the value system in a new direction. In the framework of this paper, an example of transforming the values of active management system under the new system of VUCA-world was proposed.

The authors note that this structural and cultural characteristic of the housing and utilities company, being an integral component of the company's innovation potential, is complex and applies to all categories of employees. It is important to consider this issue in relation to managers, specialists, and workers. The set of measures depending on the group of employees, management level can vary according to differentiated profiles of activity/passivity of the organizational culture of the enterprise. All changes that are carried out within the organizational and management component and are caused by environmental factors should be carried out in harmony with the changes related to the technical and technological base of the enterprise. It should be considered that the formation of active organizational culture, caused by environmental conditions, occurs at all stages of the life cycle of the enterprise: from formation and establishment, prosperity to crisis and liquidation, so this direction should be constantly given considerable attention.

Modern management science is associated with a large volume of applied research and development, significant involvement of intellectual potential and experience of experts offering scenarios for the development of management systems. The most important part of this potential is the expert community, which can ensure independence and competitiveness of the country in the next decade through the creation of an effective system of building up and the fullest use of innovations in management science and practice.

Challenges of the modern BANI-world (fragility, anxiety, non-linearity of development, “uncertain uncertainty”) have strengthened the need to create conditions for the full utilization of expert potential, which possesses various technologies and techniques – design thinking (solving old problems with new methods using project, systemic, critical thinking). The combination of heterogeneous formats and management tools to achieve the most useful result with semantic content, applied in project management, is a new methodology for the formation of management trends of the future and is called in this article – synectic-semantic modeling.

The methodology is designed to ensure the development of the intellectual potential of the country, territories and to form conditions for research and development, corresponding to the modern principles of organization of scientific, innovative activity and the best

world management practices. Improving the efficiency, professionalism and quality of the expert community is one of the basic conditions for the implementation of modern public policy, the general framework of those systemic transformations that will ensure the solution of issues of socio-economic development of the country and the world.

Modern research and expert formats are used according to the problem-thematic principle and include participants performing functional tasks aimed at solving fundamental and applied problems and transferring knowledge and technologies. Such formats are used to bring together complementary competencies and infra-structural capabilities of participants to solve project problems in a variety of management systems. Experts using modern research formats often solve their own tasks, while not making a tangible contribution to the achievement of strategic goals and priorities of development of various spheres and sectors of the economy.

This circumstance has led to the idea that it is necessary to form a new effective methodology for shaping the future. The methodology of using synectic-semantic analysis in management projects, in the opinion of all parties, should be one of the relevant in the conditions of “maximum” certainty in the use of management decisions and used for the development of various areas of activity: management, education, research, innovation, educational and expert, – by achieving high-quality results in all areas and studying positive and negative experience.

Synectics allows you to create conditions for penetrating deep perspectives through an unusual consideration of external impassable things, suggesting going beyond the scope of ordinary observation. Synectic-semantic modeling is aimed at the fastest adaptation to new conditions. As modern management practice shows, modeling of future management trends, with the participation of the expert community, is also a kind of trend [4, p. 14]. The tasks of applying the synectic-semantic modeling methodology in project management should include:

- providing a value-ideological basis for the use of research formats;
- providing conditions for the formation of a project management “ecosystem”;
- semantic content of new research formats;
- formation of an innovative system of resource provision for project implementation;
- ensuring the effectiveness and efficiency of management.

The effects of implementing the above methods include the following:

- large-scale integration of the potential of higher education and public authorities in the formation of a research agenda for solving practice-oriented problems with the participation of experts;
- development of human resources for management systems.

The considered methodology contributes to the formation of technology for achieving the desired result (the desired future) “here and now”, i.e., today, and not in the distant future. The use of synectic-semantic modeling in project management increases the efficiency of

the management system due to its complexity, innovation and focus on the result with semantic content. Synectic-semantic modeling (identification and formation of a priority version of the future, mission, purpose and semantic content – “the meaning of life”) is a new management methodology that involves the implementation of communication that allows participants to agree on the semantic content of the image of the future (the desired image of the future that most fully satisfies the interests and needs of the subject of management), to agree on priority values, goals, objectives and actions in its context and to form trends in the present [5, p. 12].

The principles of synectic-semantic modeling include: the future depends on the efforts made, it can be created; the future is variable – it does not stem from the past, but depends on the decisions of experts, stakeholders; the trend must be felt physically, emotionally; there are areas in relation to which forecasts can be made, but in general the future cannot be predicted reliably, it is possible to prepare or prepare the future as we want to see it, “here and now”. [6, p. 12].

The following tools used in synectic-semantic modeling are designed to provide the greatest effect: Delphi; Scenario; SWOT; Brainstorming; Reverse (or retro) forecast; Panel discussions; Game simulations; Structural, multi-criteria, cluster, and other types of analysis; Critical technologies method; “Inevitable future” (“Designing the future”). Let's consider the methodology of conducting synectic-semantic modeling in project management. The main participants of synectic-semantic modeling are leading experts in the modeled sphere. The most effective format for using the methodology is discussion in mini-clusters at round tables. Algorithm for conducting:

- participants sit at “round tables” in a mixed composition;
- the event is moderated by a moderator who ensures general management of the application
- of the methodology. In addition, moderators are present at each “round table”, their task is to ensure compliance with the timing and active communication of experts;
- communication takes place in an open informal setting on a given topic, event participants exchange opinions, develop solutions;

The conceptual and categorical apparatus used during the event:

- synectic-semantic modeling is a method that allows you to agree on the image of the future and your actions on the way to achieving it;
- trend is a phenomenon that already exists today and influences the management system in the future;
- innovation is a constant reformulation and redistribution of tasks - within the worlds of new opportunities [7, p. 201];
- synectic-semantic solution is a systemic proposal for the implementation of effective tools for overcoming (localizing) risky situations aimed at forming a management trend.

The purpose of synectic-semantic modeling: to identify competitive results of implementing an inno-

vative management trend based on the study of the participants' opinions. The tasks of synectic-semantic modeling in project management:

- 1) discussion and formulation by participants of “round tables” of trends, main opportunities and threats in implementing a management trend;
- 2) discussion and development of solutions to improve the effectiveness of activities to form a management trend;
- 3) discussion of issues of responsibility of the expert community in ensuring the achievement of results;
- 4) implementation of effective mechanisms of teamwork;
- 5) discussion of the main approaches to motivation to work, achieving results.
- 6) development of project solutions – the answer to the question: “What problem (problems) does the formed trend solve?”.

Let's consider the mechanism for implementing the methodology. It includes several stages. The stages of synectic-semantic modeling are called semantic steps:

- 1) The moderator sets the participants of the event the format of the work; Greeting the participants of the event.

1 Meaningful Tact – Introduction. (Answering the question “Who am I?” “The meaning of my life?”, “Why am I here?”) – 20 minutes.

1.1. Inter Tact activity: Physical and emotional sensation of the implemented trend (example, new technologies of setting goals, through archery training (darts) for focusing, etc.). – 10 minutes.

During Meaningful Tact 2 – the participants of the “round tables” formulate trends in management – 15 minutes.

- 1) The moderator gives the participants of each “round table” the task of formulating at least 3 trends within 15 minutes.

2) Following the discussion, a speaker from each table speaks and announces the management trends that have been formed; (Table 1).

3) The project team implementing the methodology (hereinafter referred to as the project team) includes the named trends in the register (except for repeating ones) and displays them on the screen in a random sequence.

Table 1.

Management trends		
No	Trend name	Validity period
1		
2		
3		

At the 3rd Semantic Step – participants of the clusters – “round tables” formulate “opportunities” and “threats” of the trends being formed – 15 minutes.

Implementation algorithm:

- 1) The moderator gives the task to the participants of each “round table” to formulate at least 3 “opportunities” and “threats” within 15 minutes.

2) Following the discussion, a speaker from each table speaks out and announces the results (Tables 2 and 3).

3) The proposed results are included in the register by the technology group and displayed on the common screen in a random sequence.

Table 2.

Opportunities	
No	Name

Table 3.

Threats	
No	Name

Meaningful Tact 4 allows participants to identify interested parties (stakeholders) and their interests in the implementation of management trends – 15 minutes. Implementation algorithm:

1) The moderator invites participants at each table to identify stakeholders in the formation of trends within 15 minutes (tables 5 and 6);

2) Following the discussion, a speaker from each table speaks and announces the results of the Meaningful Tact.

Table 5.

Stakeholders (supporting the trend)	
Stakeholders	Interest

Table 6.

Stakeholders (negatively related to the trend)	
Stakeholders	Interest

At the 5th Semantic Tact, work is carried out to formulate priority project ideas for trend formation (table 7). Clustering of ideas for the formation of management trends is carried out – 45 minutes. After a break (20 minutes), project ideas are selected by voting for them by the participants.

1) following the discussion, a speaker from each table speaks and announces the results of the Tact.

Table 7.

Project ideas for the formation of management trends	
No	Description of the idea for the trend
1	
2	
3	

Reflection (20 minutes). At this stage of the work, experts describe their condition and well-being in one word and evaluate the result in one sentence (“briefly and to the point”). “Roadmaps” for trend development can be formed.

In conclusion, it is important to emphasize that the modern system of using and developing the potential of experts in the field of management, its focus is the formation and development of a qualitatively new level of methodology, with a different semantic content, meeting the requirements of consumers, employers, the state, and society, allowing for the formation of innovative management trends. Innovations arise in complex and unstable conditions; success here is achieved by those who manage to recognize the necessary signals in an ocean of noise.

To successfully create something new in such circumstances, you need to follow a structured approach. New methods are most effective when accompanied by instant feedback from an expert who can look at the problem from a different angle and offer possible solutions.

Conclusions and prospects for further developments.

Acceleration of technological innovations in combination with major economic, social, demographic, and legislative changes requires a flexible response. The pace of change has never been as high as in the modern world. A peculiar trend of the VUCA and BANI worlds is that trends replace each other within a day or even hours. They change while we study them.

Which emphasizes the special importance of managing this process. The relevance of using the methodology is confirmed by the formation of the following management trends (formed according to the mechanism discussed in the article): the creation of “interaction ecosystems” in the state and municipal service, the use of “road maps” in the implementation of projects and programs, digitalization of management, the introduction of “digital etiquette” in management activities.

According to the authors, it is the experts who see all the essential, sometimes contradictory, aspects of the problem and find new solutions that go beyond and significantly improve the existing conditions for the development of management systems, in connection with which the principle of reliance on one's own strengths and resources becomes decisive in the existence and development of expert potential in management science and practice.

The task of introducing a new approach to the selection, scaling and replication of new effective methods, experience and management practices is becoming especially relevant in the conditions of the modern world. An example of the introduction of a new approach in management science and practice is the methodology presented in the article.

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